

Role of Artificial Intelligence in Constructing a Meta Market for Healthcare Sector to Overcome Marketing Myopia

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on understanding the role of Artificial Intelligence in constructing a Meta Market in the healthcare sector by integrating four critical domains: health insurance, health care services, pharmacies, and hospitality (Book a Hotel). The conceptual Meta Market aims to overcome marketing myopia by offering a unified platform that prioritizes patient convenience and societal well-being. By consolidating these sectors, it will simplify access to resources, streamline processes, and provide a one-stop solution for patients. This innovation seeks to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and transform the healthcare experience while promoting sustainable growth in the sector and it will also solve many problems in the domain of health care.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Meta Market and Health Care.

Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence is the outcome of computer system and information technology and machine learning to execute work that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, decision making etc. AI plays a vital role in creating a Meta Market by automating tasks, customizing customer requirements and experiences by streamlining the operations, marketing, sales and customer service to enhance customer satisfaction, Meta Market is a customer-centric virtual market that offers closely related products or services belonging to the same industry or diverse set of industries. It strives to cater for the similar needs of diversified customers under one roof. Meta-markets provide customers with a one-stop shop for all their needs – making them an essential part of the modern digital commerce landscape. Marketing myopia is the tendency of businesses to define their market so narrowly as to miss opportunities for growth.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To understand the role of Artificial Intelligence in creating Meta Market.
2. To understand the current scenario in Health Care Sector.
3. To gain overall insights about consumer (patient) preferences / behaviour while availing Health Care Services.

Scope of the Study:

- The study is restricted to Health Care Sector covering Health Insurance, Health Care Services, Pharmacies and Hospitality in case of Medical Tourism.
- The study is limited to the geographical area of Bhiwandi.

Significance of the Study:

- The study will help by constructing a pragmatic Meta Market which will serve the customers (patient) to avail Health Care Services effortlessly.

- The study will help to identify the problems and suggest solutions accordingly with respect to Health Care Sector.
- The constructed Meta Market will overcome Marketing Myopia which is marketing short sightedness of Healthcare players by given importance to the customers and not undermining their right of Health Care Services thereby improving the productivity of hospitals and compelling them to think of the long term instead of the short term.

Research Methodology:

- Type Of Study: Descriptive Research Study.
- Type Of Questionnaire: Structured type of questionnaire with limited probing questions.
- Type Of Analysis: Quantitative analysis.
Data was collected by survey with the help of questionnaire.
- Sources Of Information: This report is based on the primary as well as secondary data source of information.
- Sampling Procedure:
 - a. Sample Method: Convenience Sampling
 - b. Sample Size: 100 (Individual Customers)
 - c. Sample Area: Bhiwandi
 - d. Data Collection Method: Survey Method

Research Findings:

- Only 6% of the respondents are very satisfied, 51% of respondents are satisfied with Current Service of Hospitals, 31% of them are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 10% are dissatisfied and 2% are very dissatisfied.
- 3% of the respondents are very satisfied, 41% of respondents are satisfied with the cost of treatment at various Hospitals. Whereas, only 25% are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 24% are dissatisfied and 7% of them are very dissatisfied.
- 7% of the respondents are very satisfied, 54% of respondents are satisfied with the locations

of the Hospital. Whereas 23% of them are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, 14% are dissatisfied and 2% are very dissatisfied.

- A maximum of 53% of respondents are aware of various services provided by hospitals. Whereas, 30% can't Say and 17% do not know.
- Only 7% of respondents strongly agree with the Statement that they are satisfied with the overall Health care services provided by the Hospitals. Whereas, 48% agree, 31% neither agree nor disagree and 12% disagree and 2% strongly disagree.
- Only 5% of respondents strongly agree that it is easy to settle Medical Insurance Claims. Whereas, 39% agree, 34% neither agree nor disagree and 20% disagree and 2% strongly disagree.
- Only 11% of respondents strongly agree, 53% of people agree that they are satisfied with discounts provided by local Pharmacy available at the Hospitals. Whereas, 15% neither agree nor disagree, 18% disagree and 3% strongly disagree.
- 100% of respondents would like to have a market place which will cater as a platform serving Health Care Services, Health Insurance and Pharmacy under one Roof.
- 43% of respondents will be influenced by the Quality of Health Care Services to opt for such Market Place. Whereas, 27% will opt for Convenience and 25% for pricing. Only 5% will opt for Post Treatment Service.

Rationale of Artificial Intelligence in Constructing a Meta Market:

The paper sums up the critical and dire need of AI is a must to create a Meta Market in the Health Care Sector, thereby providing all related services to

the customers under one roof. The constructed Meta Market will help the customers (patients) in availing effective and efficient health care treatments from the hospital with appropriate medicines from the right vendor (Pharmacies) and getting a hassle free Health Insurance Claims Settlement. The efforts are to create a Meta Market through this study is to enable customers to login on a Meta Market website and getting their admission into the proper hospital depending on the nature of their treatment requirement. The Meta Market will suggest a proper Hospital which will be expertising in that branch of Medicine and will book the necessary service along with checking the status of their Health Insurance and there by liaisoning with the Health Insurance Companies and thereby settling the claim for the patients.

The constructed Meta Market will also help in a scenario where a hospital is facing a shortage of medicine or a super speciality medicine which will be required to treat the patient by arranging that particular medicine from a network of Pharmacies which are associated with the Meta Market. Further, the Meta Market will also focus on Health/ Medical Tourism by incorporating Hotels for enabling the lodging aspect of relatives. It is evident that Artificial Intelligence is required to create a Meta

Market that will bring all the necessary components of health care under one digital umbrella.

Conclusion:

Eventually, We can conclude that a Meta Market is required in a Health Care Sector so that no patient should be undermined of their rights to get prompt, efficient, effective and quality Health Care Services, thereby nullifying the Marketing Myopia of Hospitals, Health Insurance Companies and Pharmacies, which leads to a metamorphosis in intent of these players in healthcare, which is thinking long term instead of short term which will help the society and nation at large.

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